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Research of students' behavior in the financial market depending on the level of mathematical knowledge

KEYWORDS

economic experiment,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Present scientific research resorts to experiments to identify the motives of a particular behavior, primarily in the financial sector. This article aims to reveal the dependence of students' behavior in the simulated financial market on their level of **mathematical knowledge**.

Materials and Methods. The data of the present study includes the results of an experimental session conducted among students of the economics program. At the first stage, a mathematical test was conducted with tasks of the school final exams. The second stage was a model of the financial market where participants could sell and buy shares in 10 rounds; at the end of the game, the incomes of the players were compared. Three mechanisms to analyze the obtained data were used. A cloud of players' disposable funds distribution was constructed, along with income changes dynamics over time and the number of transactions in each round of the game. Next, correlation matrices were generated for the entire game and for its individual rounds. Finally, an econometric model was developed, with the player's available funds as the explained variable and their score on a mathematical test as the regressor.

Results and discussion. The results reveal that knowledge of mathematics can really influence income in the financial market, which is confirmed for our sample. The coefficient in the econometric model is significant at the 5% level and equals 48.84. In other words, an increase in a score in mathematics by 1 will entail an increase in the player's income by 48.84 coins. The coefficient of determination is 0.15, which indicates the quality of the fit of the model at 15%. Considering that the analysis uses only one factor and does not take into account other aspects that could affect the behavior of players in the market, this is a fairly high value.

Conclusion. The authors came to the conclusion that students demonstrate differences in income received in the financial market model, which, among other things, may be due to different levels of mathematical knowledge. Mathematical knowledge means the skills to use logical construction and more accurate forecasting, the probabilities of events. In the future, it is planned to scale the experiment for a larger sample and increase the representativeness of the results.

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INTRODUCTION

The financial sector of the economy provides services to firms and individuals, and its share is quite large – for instance, according to the World Federation of Exchanges for 2020, the volume of financial instruments on the New York Stock Exchange and NASDAQ amounted to 17.8 and 12.7 trillion USD, respectively [1]. Financial markets are a platform for various investment strategies and for successful and unsuccessful practices for predicting the value of assets.

Interest in behavioral strategies is wide in scientific research [2–4]. Today, the emphasis on modeling the behavior of players in the financial market is becoming relevant in order to predict the behavior of various agents. In our opinion, an experiment is appropriate for this study, because such study, in addition to identifying financial motives, allows linking link academic issues, namely, the different level of mathematical knowledge of students with behavior in the financial markets and the calculation of income received from the chosen behavior option.

The article aims to reveal the dependence of students' behavior in the simulated financial market on the level of mathematical knowledge.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our data includes the results of an experimental session conducted among 26 third-year students of the UrFU Institute of Economics and Management. The experiment consisted of two stages:

1) Mathematical test of 8 questions. The tasks were taken from the 2021-2022 BSE and USE exams (see Appendix 1).

2) The second stage was a model of the financial market where participants could sell and buy shares. Initially, each player was given a budget of 225 coins and 3 shares. Shares can bring dividends with a probability of 50% (20 coins per share). After the last 10th round, all shares expire (their value becomes equal to 0), and the players' income is compared by the number of coins.

Three tools were used to analyze the obtained data – a cloud of distribution of players' disposable funds, the dynamics of changes in income over time, as well as the number of transactions in each round; correlation matrices for the entire game and for its individual

rounds; an econometric model where the player's available funds act as the explained variable, and their score on a mathematical test is the regressor.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several existing scientific studies on the impact of various personal characteristics on behavior and performance in the financial market were considered. The influence of education, average exam scores, personality traits, and herd behavior factors in the financial market is examined in the available literature.

The article *Master of the Stock Market* by Kristijan Liivamagi, Tarvo Vaarmets, Tonn Talpsepp analyzes how the intellectual abilities and education of financial market participants can affect income. Educational performance is used as an indicator of the intelligence level which is measured using exam grades; the type and specialty of higher education are also taken into account. The data used by the authors covers one complete business cycle and includes information on transactions and performance on the national stock exchange for all Estonian individual investors, as well as data on their past education from the national register. The authors conclude that the level of mathematical knowledge and general intellectual abilities have a greater income in the financial market; people with higher education increase their income even more. Investors with a master's or doctoral degree (PhD) and people with higher education in economics or finance are more risk-averse [5].

Trader personality and trading performance: A framework and financial market experiment by Arjen van Witteloostuijn and Katrin Muehlfeld examines the influence of personality traits on behavior in the financial market. 6 personality traits are examined (locus of control, maximizing tendency, regret disposition, self-monitoring, sensation seeking and type-A/B behavior). The data is collected as a result of an economic experiment conducted among 34 economics students. The results show that different personality traits influence different components of trading behavior and hence game outcomes. Players with more relaxed personality traits trade less frequently (performance strategy). Speed-oriented, impatient types are prone to low sensitivity to environmental cues, show less propensity to use their capabilities [6].

The article *Herd Behavior in Financial Markets: An Experiment with Financial Market Professionals* by Marco Cipriani and Antonio Guarino examines behavior in the financial market under experimental conditions, but the participants are professionals, not students. The experiment is carried out in 2 stages: at the first stage, prices adjust to the flow of orders so that the herd effect should not occur; at the second stage, an uncertainty factor contributes to the herd effect. The authors note that at the first stage, the subjects are rarely gregarious, but some

still exhibit such behavior. In both approaches, contrary to what the theory predicts, subjects sometimes prefer to refrain from trading, which negatively affects price determination [7].

Literature review shows that experiments on modeling the behavior of players in the financial market can be a relevant basis for research, which makes our experiment justified.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An experiment on the influence of mathematical knowledge level on the modeling of behavior in the financial market allowed obtaining the following primary results (Table 1).

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of the experiment

Variable	Observa-tions	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation
Math score	26	3.923077	1	7	1.594466
Disposable income	260	297	10	1517	240.4955

Descriptive statistics for the collected data are provided in Table 1. As seen, the average score in mathematics was 3.92 (median value 4 points) out of 8 possible. The minimum value of the indicator is 1, and the maximum is 7. Notably, none of the participants scored the maximum in mathematics, which may indicate the need to refine the compiled test.

Moreover, Table 1 includes income (fund) statistics for all periods 1 to 10. The descriptive statistics show that the income received varies greatly (standard deviation is greater than 240) even within a small group. The hypothesis about the influence of mathematical knowledge on financial behavior (forecasting and decision making) cannot be rejected already at the level of descriptive statistics.

Table 2 presents these data separately for each round of the game.

Table 2

Player income in each round

Variable	Observa-tions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Round 1					
Disposable income	26	225	108.9374	71	491
Round 2					
Disposable income	26	225	190.6664	15	645
Round 3					
Disposable income	26	285	186.2117	21	675

Round 4					
Disposable income	26	285	236.7415	10	908
Round 5					
Disposable income	26	285	219.653	10	868
Round 6					
Disposable income	26	285	259.5401	10	1078
Round 7					
Disposable income	26	285	241.1876	10	1078
Round 8					
Disposable income	26	345	251.4236	10	1049
Round 9					
Disposable income	26	345	270.5445	10	1029
Round 10					
Disposable income	26	405	348.7375	10	1517

According to the data of one round in Table 2, the maximum disposable funds are constantly growing, slightly decreasing only in the 9th round.

It is interesting to note that from rounds 4 to 9, the value of disposable funds belonged to the same player. In the 10th round, another player gains the first place in terms of income, having increased the volume of their coins by 611 in one round. The minimum value of disposable funds, starting from the 3rd round, belonged to one person. At the same time, starting from the 4th round, the minimum value did not change. This result can be explained by the fact that, according to the rules of the experiment, there was a time limit (60 seconds per round), because of which the player simply had no time to sell and buy shares. Theoretical studies say that agents in the financial market tend to create price bubbles, which is caused by a revaluation of the value of shares in the early rounds and a sharp decline in prices towards the end of the game [4–6]. However, this phenomenon turned out to be uncharacteristic for our sample (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Deviation of average transaction prices from the real value of shares in one round

Figure 1 presents the expected dividends as the real value of the shares, the amount of individual deals made for each round, and the average amount of deals. As seen from the charts, no price bubbles were actually formed during the game, although individual transactions exceeded the real value of the shares. Only at the end the average price of transactions is higher than the real value of the shares. However, it cannot truly be considered a price bubble, as the average trade price series does not show enough dynamics over 10 rounds.

In fact, this can be explained by several reasons:

- 1) Insufficiency of sampling;
- 2) Players did not have time to understand the essence of the game;
- 3) Players adhered to subjective assessments which for the whole group turned out to be approximately the same and low, with the exception of individual outliers.

In addition, it can be assumed that students in economics are less inclined to create price bubbles; however, to confirm such conclusions, the experiment should be repeated on other groups of students.

Figure 2 Dynamics of the players' total disposable incomes by rounds

Figure 2 shows the dynamics of the total disposable income of players by round. As seen, over time, the spread in the amount of funds among the players increases. At the same time, in our sample, the biggest inequality is observed at the beginning and at the very end of the game, and from rounds 6 to 9, the spread remains approximately the same.

The obtained results will be supported by the revealed connection with mathematical knowledge, which is presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Correlation matrix between players' disposable income and maths score

Rounds	Variables	Correlation	
		Disposable income	Maths score
All	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.3238	1.0000
1	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.4559	1.0000
2	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.2899	1.0000
3	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.3182	1.0000
4	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.4109	1.0000
5	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.4712	1.0000
6	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.3983	1.0000
7	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.3295	1.0000
8	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.3664	1.0000
9	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.2281	1.0000
10	Disposable income	1.0000	
	Maths score	0.2606	1.0000

Table 3 shows that the relationship between the available funds of the players and the score in mathematics exists and is quite strong. When considering all rounds simultaneously, the correlation coefficient is 0.32. When considering them separately, the correlation coefficient varies from 0.23 in the 9th round to 0.47 in the 5th round. At the same time, in the 1st round (after the first trades) the correlation coefficient was 0.46, then there is a sharp decline to 0.29 at the end of the 2nd round and a gradual rise to the 5th round. Thus, maths knowledge is most affected in the middle of the game. The dynamics of changes in the correlation coefficient is clearly shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Dynamics of the correlation coefficient by rounds

Figure 3 shows the dynamics of the correlation between disposable funds. Throughout the experiment, the connection remains direct. The greatest strength is observed for our sample at the beginning of the game and in the middle. By the last rounds, the connection is weakening, although it remains quite strong. This result can be attributed to fairly large outliers in the last round (in the 10th round, the largest transaction value for the entire game is observed).

Figure 4 Distribution cloud of disposable incomes of players depending on the score in mathematics (for all 10 rounds)

Figure 4 shows the dependence of the amount of funds a player has on a score on a mathematical test. The distribution cloud shows a direct relationship between income and a score in mathematics – the higher the score on the test, the more money the player has. To better understand the nature of this dependence, regression models can be built for the entire sample and for individual rounds.

Table 4

Panel regression for all rounds

Random-effects GLS regression	Number of obs	=	260			
Group variable: id	Number of groups	=	26			
R-sq:	Obs per group:					
within = 0.0000	min	=	10			
between = 0.1518	avg	=	10.0			
overall = 0.1048	max	=	10			
	Wald chi2(1)	=	4.30			
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)	Prob > chi2	=	0.0382			
Profit	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Maths	48.83505	23.56376	2.07	0.038	2.650931	95.01916
_cons	105.4164	99.75871	1.06	0.291	-90.1071	300.9398
sigma_u	185.95786					
sigma_e	140.74071					
rho	.63580482	(Fraction of variance due to u_i)				

The model does not exhibit heteroscedasticity, and multicollinearity is not an issue in the study, given that only two factors are analyzed (one dependent and one explanatory variable).

Thus, based on the results of the constructed model, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) The model as a whole is significant;
- 2) The coefficient for a score in mathematics is significant at the 5% level;
- 3) Raising a score on a maths test can increase a player's equity value by 48.84 money.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that knowledge of mathematics can indeed influence returns in the financial market, which is confirmed for our sample by analysis using the three methods

described in the previous section. The coefficient in the econometric model is significant at the 5% level and equals 48.84. In other words, an increase in a score in mathematics by 1 will entail an increase in the player's income by 48.84 coins. The coefficient of determination is 0.15, which indicates the quality of the fit of the model at 15%. Considering that only one factor is used in the analysis, without accounting for other aspects that could affect market player behavior, this is a fairly high value.

The results of our study are consistent with other works. If a student who scored higher on a math test is assumed to have greater intellectual and analytical abilities, this aligns with the findings in the article Master of the Stock Market [5].

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APPENDIX

Question	Answer options	Correct answer
<p>Question 1</p> <p>Pineapples cost 100 rubles per unit. What is the maximum number of pineapples you can buy for 800 rubles, if their price is reduced by 20%?</p>	<p>1) 10; 2) 8; 3) 6; 4) 40;</p>	1) 10
<p>Question 2</p> <p>Maths teacher, Ivan Petrovich, must turn off his telephone when he teaches. Choose statements that follow from the given data.</p> <p>1) If Ivan Petrovich's phone is on, it means that he is not teaching lessons. 2) If Ivan Petrovich's phone is turned off, it means that he is teaching a lesson. 3) If Ivan Petrovich is taking a maths test, then his phone is turned off. 4) If Ivan Petrovich is not teaching a lesson, then his phone is on.</p>	<p>1) 2, 4; 2) 1, 2; 3) 1, 3; 4) 3, 4;</p>	3) 1, 3
<p>Question 3</p> <p>At the geometry exam, the student answers one question from the list of exam questions. The probability that this is a question on the topic "Inscribed circle" is 0.2. The probability that this is a question on the topic "Trigonometry" is 0.25. There are no questions that simultaneously relate to these two topics. Find the probability that a student will get a question on one of these two topics on the exam.</p>	<p>1) 0.125; 2) 0.05; 3) 0.45; 4) 1;</p>	3) 0.45
<p>Question 4</p> <p>It is known about the numbers a and b that a is greater than b. Among the inequalities listed below, choose the correct ones: In the answer, specify the number of the correct option.</p> <p>1) $a - b < -3$ 2) $b - a > 1$ 3) True 1, 2 4) $b - < 2$</p>	<p>1) Correct 1; 2) Correct 2; 3) Correct 3; 4) Correct 4;</p>	4) Correct 4
<p>Question 5</p> <p>Find the root of equation: $6(x^2) = 36x$ If the equation has more than one root, choose the smaller one.</p>	<p>1) 6; 2) 0; 3) -6; 4) 36;</p>	2) 0
<p>Question 6</p> <p>The taxi company currently has 20 cars available: 2 black, 2 yellow and 16 green. On a call, one of the cars that happened to be closest to the customer left. Find the probability that a yellow taxi will arrive to them.</p>	<p>1) 1; 2) 0.1; 3) 0.2; 4) 0.8;</p>	2) 0.1
<p>Question 7</p> <p>One of the angles of the triangle is 90 degrees. The sides adjacent to this corner are 3 and 4. Find the third side.</p>	<p>1) 7; 2) 12; 3) 5; 4) 1;</p>	3) 5;
<p>Question 8</p> <p>Which of the following statements is true?</p> <p>1) If the angle is 45°, then the vertical angle with it is 45°. 2) Any two straight lines have exactly one common point. 3) Exactly one straight line passes through any three points. 4) If the distance from a point to a straight line is less than 1, then the length of any inclined line drawn from this point to the straight line is less than 1.</p>	<p>1) Correct 1; 2) Correct 2; 3) Correct 3; 4) Correct 4;</p>	1) Correct 1

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